

THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF A CFRP LAMINATE SUBJECTED TO LOAD CYCLING AT R RATIOS FROM PURE TENSION TO PURE COMPRESSION.

T Adam, N Gathercole, B Harris and H Reiter.
School of Materials Science
University of Bath
Bath, UK.

ABSTRACT.

This paper presents the fatigue behaviour of an intermediate modulus Toray T800 carbon fibre/resin laminate with a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_5$ lay-up. It has been shown that the rates of fatigue damage in pure tension and pure compression are similar and that if the compressive element of the load cycle is weighted in the ratio of the tensile to the compressive static strengths, the stress range/life plots are co-incident. It has further been shown that the stress range/life plots for all tests cycled through zero (ie $R = -0.3, -1.0$ and -1.5), if weighted in the same way, are also co-incident and that the rate of fatigue damage under such cycling is 2.4 times that of either pure tensile pure compressive loading. An analysis of the T/C data, in which the lives of the tensile and compressive elements are compared to those obtained from pure T/T or C/C tests, shows that there is an interaction between the damage occurring in the low stress regions of tension and compression fatigue, when cycling through zero stress, which is not apparent when the loading is purely tensile purely compressive.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Much of the research that has been carried out on the fatigue behaviour of high-performance composites has been directed towards elucidating the physical mechanisms of degradation during cyclic loading and establishing the effects of material

or environmental variables on the basic fatigue response, mainly under constant stress amplitude conditions. There have been several studies of the accumulation of damage in a variety of composites, and arising out of these a number of models have been proposed that permit fatigue life predictions to be made, with varying degrees of success. A recent in-depth survey of life prediction methods⁽¹⁾, either of the kind which rank materials according to some established correlation (stress/life, strain/life etc.) or which attempt to establish a recognised pattern of degradation that allows appropriate extrapolation, suggests that most existing models are limited by dubious assumptions or lack of real knowledge of the actual degradation mechanisms.

As a basic model for prediction of life and residual properties for constant amplitude cycling, the strength/life equal rank assumption⁽¹⁾ appears to have some merit since predictions are made on the basis of relatively limited amounts of data. For variable amplitude cycling the situation is far less satisfactory. Attempts to predict behaviour following simple or complex block loading patterns have usually given non-conservative results⁽²⁾ and have established that linear cumulative damage rules are inappropriate in most circumstances^(3,4,5). In particular, Schütz and Gerharz⁽³⁾ observed that for certain types of laminates the linear damage rule predicted lives up to three times those actually measured, far too large a margin for design purposes. They suggested that this could be due to damage contributed by low stress cycles in the compressive region which is not accounted for in the Miner estimate. At present therefore, we do not appear to have a general predictive capability for variable amplitude fatigue response for high performance composite laminates, underpinned by a reasonable understanding of microstructural damage mechanisms.

In this paper the authors examine the effect of R ratio on fatigue data and offer an interpretation of the results in terms of a linear damage law.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS.

2.1 Material.

The test material consisted of 100cm x 30cm 16 ply laminated panels of $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ lay-up, fabricated from pre-impregnated Toray T800 intermediate modulus fibre in BASF (Narmco) bismaleimide resin, Rigidite 5245. Specimens 200mm x 20mm were cut with a wet cutting diamond saw and the edges ground to ensure a parallel and notch free gauge length. 50mm aluminium tabs were bonded to the ends of the specimens to

prevent grip damage.

2.2 Fatigue testing.

All fatigue testing was carried out in computer controlled Instron 1300 series servo-hydraulic machines operating under load control. The in-house designed computer control system enabled the specimens to be subjected to a preset load sequence while simultaneously recording and monitoring each load cycle. All tests, tension/tension (T/T), tension/compression (T/C), and compression/compression (C/C), were carried out at a frequency of 5Hz as previous experience⁽⁶⁾ indicated that no deleterious effects would occur at that cycling rate. Where the load cycle included a compressive component, an anti-buckling guide was used⁽⁷⁾ to constrain the test piece. With careful attention to setting up the jig with shim plates and spacers, the majority of fatigue failures occurred in the gauge length. This jig was also used to determine the compressive failure strength of the material

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

3.1 Strength measurements.

The test results for tensile and compression strengths are presented in table 1. For the tensile data, the correlation coefficient for the best fit line to a conventional two-parameter Weibull plot for 36 test results was 0.991, the median strength (failure probability of 0.5) 1.62 GPa and the Weibull modulus, m , 25.7. Whilst the test results for the compressive strength are rather few, the results nevertheless show a correlation coefficient of 0.95, a median failure strength of 0.99 GPa and a modulus, m , of 12.05.

3.2 Fatigue experiments.

The stress/life curves for the tests ($R = 0.1, -0.3, -1.0, -1.5$ and 10) are shown in fig.1. The Weibull distribution plot for fatigue data at $R = 0.1$ is shown in fig. 2 and the two parameter Weibull analysis for all the fatigue data is included in table 1, from which it can be seen that the shape parameter is very similar for all the fatigue tests.

4. DISCUSSION.

4.1 Effect of R ratio on stress/life behaviour.

The S/logN curves for T/T and C/C tests, fig. 3, show that the damage rate up to 10^7 cycles, as judged from slopes of the best fit lines through the median points, is virtually the same, with a decrease in the fatigue strength of 0.11 and 0.10 GPa per decade respectively. Both fatigue lines extrapolate approximately to the median static fracture strengths of 1.6 GPa for tension and 1.0 GPa for compression. Whilst it is difficult to obtain fatigue data substantially beyond 10^7 cycles, the few data points obtained beyond this value do not suggest a sudden down-turn in the slope of the line and extrapolation beyond 10^7 is therefore not unreasonable. The failure stress level when these lines are extrapolated through a life of 10^8 cycles could therefore be regarded as a quasi fatigue limit.

When the stress/life data of fig. 1 are replotted in terms of stress range instead of peak stress, fig. 4, the values for $R = 0.1$ and $R = -1.5$ overlap substantially, whereas those for $R = -1$ and $R = -0.3$ deviate substantially upwards, as has been observed in previous work⁽⁸⁾. However, the inference from this observation that a modest amount of compressive loading is beneficial must be questioned and will be discussed further.

As the fatigue behaviour can be related to the static strengths, and the compressive failure stress is approximately 60% of the tensile strength, the normal representation of stress range/life data for T/C cycling does not give the compressive component of the stress cycle adequate weighting in terms of damage caused. A weighting of the compressive stress components by a factor α_t/α_c , where α_t is the tensile and α_c the compressive failure strength, would allow a better comparison of the damage caused by the compression component in T/C tests at various R values.

A replot of data in fig. 3 in which the compressive component of the loading cycle has been weighted is shown in fig. 5, from which an interesting fact immediately becomes apparent. Because of the similarity in the rate of fatigue damage in T/T and C/C tests, weighting the compressive data with respect to the tensile strength makes the plots for T/T and C/C coincident, while simultaneously emphasising the marked difference in fatigue behaviour of the material in T/C compared to T/T or C/C, the former causing a much greater rate of loss in fatigue strength. A comparison of best fit lines through the data of a weighted stress range/life plot shows that under T/C conditions the rate of loss in fatigue strength is almost 2.5 times that of the rate under T/T or C/C test conditions.

If one considers that there is little or no fatigue damage occurring at stresses below what was referred to as a quasi-fatigue limit, i.e. in the range +0.8 to -0.4 GPa, there is in this region a kind of 'low damage zone'. This zone would be similar to the matrix controlled zone in Talreja's model of fatigue failure mechanisms⁽⁹⁾. The majority of the damage would then only occur when the material is subjected to cyclic stresses outside this zone, namely above +0.8 GPa or below -0.4 GPa. A replot of the data of fig. 5 in which only the stress range outside the 'low damage zone' is considered, is shown in fig. 6. The marked difference previously observed in the stress range /life plots between T/T or C/C and T/C tests is narrowed to the extent that at the higher stress ranges the data points could be regarded as falling within the same scatter band. It is only at the longer lives and lower stress ranges that the T/T and C/C test data become distinguishable from T/C tests. When the data are presented in this form the relative damage rates are almost halved with a reduction from a factor of 2.4 to 1.3. These findings lend support to the idea of the presence of a substantially damage-free stress range on either side of zero.

The apparent improvement in fatigue behaviour which a modest amount of compressive loading ($R = -0.3$) appears to bring about (fig.4) can now be accounted for. Since the compressive component lies in the 'low damage zone' it effectively adds to the stress range, although making little or no contribution to damage.

4.2 T/C testing and two block loading.

If one now considers that a T/C test is equivalent to a 2-block loading system in which the tension and compression components each comprise one block, and Miner's rule is obeyed, the total life to failure for the T/C test should equal the sum of the lives obtained from separate but equivalent T/T and C/C tests. Such an analysis is given in table 2 from which it can be seen that the Miner rule does not apply. The contribution which the tension or compression components of the T/C tests make to the failure of the specimen when the stresses are within the 'low damage zone' are seen to be minimal. The low Miner sums clearly indicate that for a fixed stress range, the fatigue damage caused by cycling through zero is more harmful than for tension or compression on its own. It can further be seen that as the R ratio becomes increasingly negative i.e. the proportion of the compressive element in the T/C test increases, the Miner sum moves towards unity.

Whilst it has been shown that by a normalisation of the compressive component for T/C tests all the data for the stress range/life plots become coincidental and show a damage

rate significantly higher than those for pure compression or tension (fig.5), even when allowance is made for the so called 'low damage zone', no obvious mechanism to explain these findings has been observed. This greater rate of fatigue damage for T/C cycling compared to T/T or C/C is highlighted by the effect on the Miner sum when separating a T/C cycle into its tension and compression components.

Since the rates of fatigue damage are substantially the same for pure tension or compression cycling, an excursion through zero has a very marked effect on fatigue life. In ud composites the 'low damage zone' is essentially matrix controlled (Talreja) with the presence of a possible fatigue limit. In a laminate containing 45 and 90 degree plies the stresses are more complex and whilst the damage incurred in the 'low damage' stress region is very little under compressive or tension forces only, the damage mechanisms would appear to be strongly interactive when subjected to a stress reversal.

No microstructural evidence has yet been found to verify the above arguments, but it is hoped that a programme of 2 and 4 block loading, at present being undertaken, will provide further information to allow a better understanding of the interaction between tension and compression loading on fatigue damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.

The authors are grateful to the Procurement Executive (Ministry of Defence) for sponsorship of this work and to Dr P T Curtis of the Royal Aerospace Establishment, Farnborough, for his advice and support.

REFERENCES.

1. PM Barnard and JB Young, MoD Contract 11494/2028-0134 XR/MAT, November (1986).
2. D Schütz and JJ Gerharz, Composites 8 245-250 (1977).
3. RJ Howe and MJ Owen, Proc Eighth Int. Reinforced Plastics Congress (BPF, London) 137-148 (1972).
4. LJ Broutman and S Sahu, Proc 24th Annual Technical Conference of SPI, paper 11D (1969)
5. JJ Gerharz, in Practical Considerations of Design, AGARD (NATO) Lecture Series no 124, paper 8 (1982)

6. CJ Jones, RF Dickson, T Adam, H Reiter and B Harris, Proc Roy Soc (London) A396 315-338 (1984)
7. PT Curtis, RAE (Farnborough) Technical Report 88012 MOD, (1988).
8. G Fernando, RF Dickson, T Adam, H Reiter and B Harris, J Mat Sci **23** 3732-3743 (1988)
9. R Talreja, Proc Roy Soc (London) A338 461-475 (1981)

Table 1. Weibull analysis of strength and fatigue data for T800/5245 $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ laminate.

Two-parameter Weibull model: $F(x;b,m) = 1 - \exp[-(x/b)^m]$, where m = modulus or shape parameter, and b = characteristic value or location parameter. b is also the median value, $m(Nf)$ in the case of fatigue lives.

Stress level	Number of data sets	Standard deviation	Weibull shape parameter, m	Weibull location parameter, $b(P=0.5)$	Correlation coefficient r
Tensile strength	36	0.07	25.73	1.62	0.991
Comp. strength	6	0.07	12.05	0.99	0.959
Fatigue stresses, σ_{max}					
R = +0.1					
1.4 GPa	8	332	1.10	276	0.960
1.3	10	8160	0.84	4623	0.978
1.2	12	212167	0.66	80320	0.978
1.1	10	479080	1.11	585133	0.985
1.0	7	3811764	0.94	3251521	0.970
0.9	5	5393022	1.59	10345099	0.978
Mean=1.04					
R = -0.3					
1.3 GPa	5	868	3.02	3119	0.949
1.2	5	6529	1.17	7639	0.966
1.1	5	62754	0.80	48590	0.994
1.0	4	96185	2.47	300893	0.990
0.9	4	283460	1.40	511952	0.940
Mean=1.77					
R = -1.0					
0.75 GPa	5	190	0.42	53	0.936
0.70	3	14642	0.34	4381	0.994
0.60	6	59732	1.22	68911	0.750
0.55	3	33303	2.77	133876	0.950
0.50	4	106411	2.65	422302	0.911
Mean=1.48					
R = -1.5					
0.50 GPa	3	1623	0.68	1133	0.896
0.47	4	8498	0.75	10120	0.978
0.40	4	188212	0.66	141817	0.966
0.33	2	1266561	0.51	853242	1.000
Mean=0.65					
R = +10					
-0.55 GPa	6	1032914	0.93	1026407	0.953
-0.60	7	126083	0.89	99787	0.930
-0.70	9	23878	1.11	22687	0.985
-0.75	5	6692	0.70	3980	0.993
Mean=0.91					

Table 2. Miner analysis of T/C data from T800/5245 $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ laminate
in terms of an equivalent 2-block loading sequence.

		Median life to failure			Miner sum		
		Tension Compression T/C	Tension only T/T	Compression only C/C	$N = N_{T/C}/N_T + N_{T/C}/N_C$		
σ_{\max}	σ_{\min}	$N_{T/C}$	$N_{T/T}$	$N_{C/C}$	$N_{T/C}/N_T$	$N_{T/C}/N_C$	N
R = -0.3							
1.2	-0.36	7.64×10^3	8.03×10^3	$> 10^7$	0.09	< 0.01	0.09
1.1	-0.33	4.86×10^4	5.85×10^5	$> 10^7$	0.08	< 0.01	0.08
1.0	-0.30	3.01×10^5	3.25×10^7	$> 10^7$	0.09	< 0.01	0.09
0.9	-0.27	5.12×10^5	1.03×10^5	$> 10^7$	0.05	< 0.01	0.05
R = -1.0							
0.70	-0.70	4.00×10^3	$> 10^7$	2×10^4	< 0.01	0.20	0.20
0.60	-0.60	6.90×10^4	$> 10^7$	2×10^5	< 0.01	0.35	0.35
0.55	-0.55	1.34×10^5	$> 10^7$	1×10^6	< 0.01	0.13	0.13
0.50	-0.50	4.22×10^5	$> 10^7$	2×10^6	< 0.01	0.21	0.21
R = -1.5							
0.47	-0.70	1.00×10^4	$> 10^7$	2×10^4	< 0.01	0.50	0.50
0.40	-0.64	1.40×10^5	$> 10^7$	4×10^5	< 0.01	0.36	0.36
0.33	-0.50	8.50×10^5	$> 10^7$	2×10^6	< 0.01	0.13	0.13

Figure 1. Stress/life data at various R ratios for T800/5245 CFRP laminate.

Figure 2. Weibull distribution plots of fatigue data for T800/5245 CFRP laminate, R = 0.1.

Figure 3. Stress/median life data at various R ratios for T800/5245CFRP laminate.

Figure 4. Stress range/life data at various R ratios for T800/5245 CFRP laminate.

Figure 5. Weighted stress range/life curve for T800/5245 CFRP laminate.

Figure 6. Weighted and reduced stress range/life curve for T800/5245 CFRP laminate.